

PLEASURES THROUGH MOBILE APPLICATIONS: INVESTIGATING THE USER-SYSTEM INTERACTION

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to identify the kinds of pleasures involved in the interaction of mobile application users and how users with different levels of experience may differ in their emotional response, influencing the design for experience. To develop a product or service that a consumer has some kind of emotion: this goal is directly related to design for experience, which is defined as an activity to map processes that support these experiences. For this study, we selected the photo-sharing application Instagram and we used the theoretical model proposed by Jordan (2000), which classifies the pleasures in four types: physical, psychological, social and ideological. Exploratory factor analysis results show the existence of two major emotional responses (“appreciation” and “security”). Anova results show that users with more experience have higher emotional response “appreciation”. Finally, regression results show that both “appreciation” and “security” emotional responses are important predictors of user satisfaction.

Keywords: Design for experience; Pleasure; Mobile applications; Interaction.

INTRODUCTION

The activity of design, that used to be limited to logo design, product, or interior, extends today to the experience customers have with products, services and environments. According to Moritz (2005); Celaschi and Deserti (2007), design has changed its scope and goes beyond the production of artifacts: it is also being used to design the processes and systems that add value and that underlie the experiences. For these authors, design is involved in

the development of strategies that is recognized as a catalyst for business and must be integrated from conception of an idea to completion of a project.

Based on this previous discussion, the focus is on creating a product or a service that awakens in the consumer some sort of emotional feeling. This goal is directly related to the design for experience, which is defined as an activity to map processes that support these experiences, from the philosophy of the project to monitor the returns of this project (Moritz, 2005). It can be argued that design is involved in the whole process of designing a product or service, ensuring to the user that it will give them the desired return.

According to Kurtgozu (2003), the term design for experience comes into existence from the concern with the emotion and experience that is manifested through the interaction of people with products and services. That is, design for experience is involved in all dimensions during the process of creation of a product or service, directly influencing human emotional experience. For McLellan (2000, p. 01), the goal of design for experience is to “orchestrate experiences that are not only functional and purposeful, but also engaging, compelling, memorable, and enjoyable”. In this sense, the term design for experience can be considered as a prediction or a response of the emotions that will arise after the user experience.

There are several ways to describe the different emotional responses in interaction among users and products or services, such as appraisals theory (Demir et al., 2009), levels of emotional processes (Norman, 2006), and the types of pleasures (Jordan, 2000), which was selected to be worked on this paper. From

this perspective, the focus of this paper is to identify the kinds of pleasures involved in the interaction of mobile application users and how these pleasures may influence the design for emotional experience.

For this reason, this work is structured based on two main areas: emotional experience, and user-system interaction. To illustrate the user-system interaction it will be presented the results of a survey conducted with users of the photo-sharing application Instagram and, finally, the discussion will be presented among the main topics mentioned above and the research results.

DESIGN FOR EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE

Design for experience aims to create products or services focusing on the user, the one that will live an experience, whether it is positive or negative as they relate to a product or a service. According to Freire (2009), the focus is the development of mechanisms that supports the designer to involve the user and the product or service in an emotionally valuable way.

This concept of designing to influence the quality of people's lived experience is useful to describe the expansion of design functions. Pine and Gilmore (1998) believe in design for experience as a new type of economic offer, distinctive of product and service design, and they call it the experience economy. For Van Amstel (2008), the term implies a holistic approach, that is, the focus is given on a systemic view of the individual experience. It reinforces that design for experience is connected directly with the organization strategy as it encourages consumers to be involved with a product or service.

However, for Suri (2003), the experience on its own is personal and although designers can influence it, it cannot be designed. For the author, many aspects of the experience – those affected by people internal states, moods or context – are independent of the designer's control. However, according to the author, experience is also influenced by factors that designers can control: the sensory qualities such as sound, smell, mass and texture; and behavioral qualities, such as feedback, rhythm, and logic, that is, all the expressive qualities inherent in the products, environments, facilities and services that are designed.

Conceptually, according to Suri (2003), putting people and their experiences at the center of attention is a simple way to organize and integrate the expressions of ideas about design. As the author mentions, although it is not possible to control people subjective experiences, design expressions can be adjusted, such as behavioral and formal qualities, to influence emotions and experiences appropriately.

According to Freire (2009), design for experience does not intend to create specific stimuli. There must be a vision of the whole for the designed experience provoke some kind of stimulus in an environment (concrete or abstract), allowing to create new opportunities for products or services. In addition, it creates opportunities for people to feel it, somehow, in any environment. Norman (2006) argues that the problems that may occur with any type of product are always the result of failures in the design project and not the user fault.

In these interactions there are three interferences from experience such as: aesthetic experience, meaning experience, and emotional experience. The aesthetic experience is lived through one or more human senses. The meaning experience occurs when there is attribution of symbolic meanings in the interaction, according to Desmet and Hekkert (2007).

The emotional experience, which will be worked on this paper, is caused by the evaluation of the aesthetic or symbolic and contributes to the process of decision making. Desmet and Hekkert (2007) define experience as any affective experience involved in the relationship between an individual and a product or service. This definition is linked to affective experience, that is, the terms "affect" and "experience" in this case are considered conceptually the same. The reference given is through the affective state, as defined by the authors, when there is any kind of experience that involves a pleasant or unpleasant perception, for example.

In addition, users build their experience through their own features. Desmet and Hekkert (2007) exemplify these characteristics as the user's skills, personality, cultural values etc. The authors highlight the features of products such as their shapes, textures, colors,

etc., where "all actions and processes that are involved, such as physical actions and perceptual and cognitive processes (such as: see, explore, use, remember, compare, and understand), contribute to the experience" (Desmet and Hekkert 2007, p. 58).

The main theoretical approaches that aim to account for the study of emotions and cognitive implications in design for experience are mainly in Jordan's (2000) four kinds of pleasures: physical, psychological, social and ideological; in Norman's (2006) three levels of emotional processing: visceral, behavioral and reflective; and the appraisals theory, represented by Demir et al. (2009), but widely studied by many authors, whose root is the work of Magda Arnold (1960). The focus of this paper is Jordan's (2000) approach, because it offers an emotional structure that can be related to the interaction provided by the mobile application and what pleasures it evokes on the users.

Also, we visualize the approach proposed by Forlizzi and Battarbee (2004) on the concepts of interaction and experience. According to the authors, the interaction between user and product can be described in three ways: fluent, cognitive and expressive.

The first one, fluent interaction, concerns familiar interactions: customary, that occurs automatically, without requiring great involvement and user attention. The second is cognitive interaction, in contrast to the fluent, is characterized by demanding a critical engagement of the user with the object of interaction. This interaction can result in learning, with a positive interaction, where the user ability to interact with the product is in their past experiences; or conflicting interaction, due to the lack of this ability, because it is something new or complex. The third, expressive interaction, is characterized by the establishment of relations with the product or any of its aspects. In this interaction the user is involved with the product causing adjustments, modifications, customizations, that he will express in a straightforward manner, establishing a bond of relationship between the user and product.

Later, Forlizzi and Battarbee (2004) list the types of interactions with experiences that build the product. The authors synthesize in experience, an experience and co-experience. In experience, the user constantly

evaluates the objectives relating to other people, objects or environments, in a continuous stream of conscious action. An experience is characterized by start and end and can therefore be classified or named, and it often inspires behavioral and emotional changes in user. Co-experience refers to experience a social context where it is created or shared with others and is related to the presence of physical or virtual people.

Technology today plays an important role as the means of interpersonal interaction. The new media allow people to create, edit, share and view content, establishing itself as a means of social interaction. Therefore, the co-experience encompasses both the experience in the sense of continuous flow, automated, and an experience that demands cognitive involvement and expressive user.

However, design for experience demands to understand aspects of a product beyond those that characterize the physical and cognitive actions of an individual (Jordan, 2000). Forlizzi and Battarbee (2004) posits that emotions play a central role in human experience, pointing out that for design, emotions fill the gap between users and products, and that these emotions establish the ways in which the interaction is planned, serving as a resource for understanding and communication about what is experienced.

The study of human factors in product-user interaction, according to Jordan (2000) should focus on the pleasures rather than solely on usability aspects, to ensure a holistic view of the user. Hierarchically, pleasures are in last instance on user needs. It takes the interaction with the product have gone through the first functional factors, then the factors of usability, and then there is the involvement of pleasure.

Jordan (2000) defines pleasure in interacting with a product as a causal effect classified into practical benefits, emotional, and hedonistic. The practical benefits are those resulting from the tasks performed by the product. The emotional benefits are related to how the product affects the mood of the user. The benefits are those related to the hedonistic pleasures and aesthetic sense.

Pleasures can be classified, according to Jordan

(2000), in two ways: need pleasures and pleasures of appreciation. Need pleasures are those that take the individual to a state of dissatisfaction to satisfaction. Pleasures of appreciation, however, are those obtained from a particular source and that are not related to the current state of satisfaction: it is identified as simply something pleasant in itself, without the previous existence of a need to be satisfied. From this perspective, pleasures can be understood as the elimination of, or absence of pain, and also to provide positive feelings.

Based on that, we will look briefly at the definitions of the four kinds of pleasures, proposed by Jordan, (2000) that structures the possibilities of emotional experiences, namely: physical pleasure, social pleasure, ideological pleasure, and psychological pleasure.

Physical pleasure is related to the perception of human sensory organs: experiences that involve touch, smell, taste, are experiences that can result in physical pleasures. If a product has not been properly designed on these aspects, it can cause negative effects on users, such as discomfort or irritation. If these aspects are well considered and resolved, the user may feel relief by the lack of problem or simply may not notice.

Social pleasure is related to the individual's involvement with other people or with the society as a whole. A specific product may be an agent of social interaction that causes pleasure to share moments, thoughts, attitudes, or desires. A product can cause comfort or discomfort in social relationships; it can establish a sense of belonging to a particular group, claiming a social identity, allowing to the individual the feeling of being socially accepted.

Psychological pleasure refers to cognitive and emotional individual reactions. A product that requires cognitive actions from the user, can trigger positive or negative reactions depending on the degree of ease or the user's ability to use the product. If the product does not provide easy ways to use on the first contact, there is a good chance of user frustration. The perceived effect plays an important role in the design. Some results may be linked to the emotional capacity of the

individual to perceive through the signs given by the product if it is reliable, fun, or dangerous, for example.

A person ability to perceive the product and have an emotional response from it is directly related to cultural values or natural human instincts. The user can see a product differently given their past experiences and habits, and can respond instinctively to color signals as relaxing or stimulating. Emotional responses are also related to the context where the product is used, depending on time, moods, or other individuals who influence the emotional user experience. According to Norman (1988), experience with a product can extend the user cognitive ability, attribute that he calls "world knowledge", which is a distinction between knowledge that individuals have in their minds and knowledge stored on external devices. Examples of this concept are smartphones, tablets, or laptops that allow you to access content that may be beyond our cognitive abilities and that can lead us to experience pleasure.

Ideological pleasure concerns the values related to life situations, personal aspirations, and social morality. The values ultimately define the products characteristics and types of interactions and experiences obtained from them. Thus, the strategies may involve design and driving it to the values of user groups. Some products may represent the spirit of an era and express ideologies such as rebellion, freedom, and compassion. The postmodern phenomenon can significantly influence on tastes and individuals values, where the rank and value judgments become less significant. The distinction between popular culture and high art elite become less clear, as well as the gender gap in culture.

Based on the proposal of the four types of pleasures in user-product interaction (Jordan, 2000), and considering other parallel approaches revisited throughout the study, this article will discuss an empirical study on the use of the application Instagram.

INSTAGRAM APP

Launched in July 2008 the App Store is a service for iPhone, iPod and iPad Touch, created by Apple Inc., that allows users to browse and download applications from the iTunes Store. Today, more than

50.000 titles are available in the store, between paid and free applications, divided into 20 categories from games to business applications.

In the "photo and video" category is inserted the object of this study: the application Instagram. Created in October 2010, Instagram completed its one year anniversary in 2011, with over 12 million users (Teixeira, 2011).

The software is free and allows users to take pictures with their mobile devices and add visual effects. After that step, users can post photos in their Instagram accounts or social network sites as Facebook, Twitter and Flickr. Thus was formed a network of professional and amateur photographers, with an interface (figure 1), that allows authors to follow their favorites, "like" and check the popular publication photos.

Figure 1. Instagram's graphic interface.

Besides simply take pictures, the main feature of the service is the ability to apply filters effects on images. There are seventeen different filters that give a classic look of photographs captured on traditional film and developed with chemicals, emphasizing color and shading and simulating old photos. According to Stone (2011), the software's success is due to the context in which it was released: it became a habit for people to share their lives while it happens. Still, the emergence of mobile devices and wireless Internet networks, allows people to publish their photos immediately after shooting.

Bolt (2011) analyzes the popularity of Instagram in three aspects: quality, audience and constraints. On the aspect of quality, the author believes the application offers the same quality and visual appeal of other softwares, and even with low resolution it has the ability to make users feel some artistic merit to

their images. According to the author, Instagram offers a good user experience due to the quality of the filters and the experience of posting photos. As for the public, Bolt (2011) points out that more than a social network, the application should be considered as a window to access places and objects that people don't normally get to see.

About the constraints, Bolt (2011) believes that the idea of having one image at a time, when making a publication, is a project decision that seeks to generate more value and meaning to each image, improving the viewing experience. Another constraint the author points out is that even though everyone uses the same features of filters and lenses of Apple devices cameras, users have a great creative ability.

In summary, Bolt (2011) believes that the constraints, combined with the quality and the audience, are the aspects that make the Instagram app so interesting.

METHOD

This study focuses on users of Apple apps due to its popularity. The Instagram app was chosen by the iTunes as the best app for iPhone in 2011. The main objective of this study is to understand the emotional responses of users when using the Instagram app. More specifically, with different levels of experience in using the app and how these emotional responses might influence the design for experience. The methodological approach was quantitative, using statistical inference techniques to assess the product pleasurability feeling related to the referred object, based on Jordan's theory (2000). This research option can be explained by the interest on describing the pleasure components and the correlation among themselves, using factor analysis as the main statistical method technique.

It was used a questionnaire based on Jordan's (2000) pre-prepared questionnaire for quantification of product pleasurability. Using a Likert-scale varying from 1 ("totally disagree") to 5 ("totally agree"), it was developed twelve self-reported measures to capture the following emotional responses: 1) I feel stimulated when using this product; 2) I feel free by having this product; 3) I feel excited when I use this app; 4) I'm satisfied by using this app; 5) I feel I can always have

this app; 6) I would miss this app if I could not have it anymore; 7) I trust this app; 8) I feel proud of this app; 9) I enjoy this app; 10) I relax when I use this app; 11) I feel enthusiastic when using this app; 12) I feel I should be cautious with this app. In addition, we developed one self-reported measure to capture the experience of users with the Instagram app.

The data collection procedure was based on the internet social networks, like Facebook and Twitter. Invitations were sent for our social network contacts to participate on this study and the link for the questionnaire was available in our Facebook page for 30 days, so respondents could participate whenever they wanted. It was obtained a total of 80 responses but only 49 were ready to be used for statistical analysis. The other 31 questionnaires were discarded due to excess of missing data.

Our final sample of 49 respondents is characterized by 47% of women. Age of most respondents (67%) varies between 20 and 29 years old, and approximately 88% of all respondents have a graduated or post-graduated degree. From all respondents, 27% are students, 16% are scholars, 37% work as lawyers, accountants, physicians, and others.

Our analytical approach is as follows: we run an exploratory factor analysis to find common relationship among the emotional responses and reduce them to a few number of factors, and, then, we check for consistency of responses. After extracting some factors, we tested the mean differences of such emotional responses factors for groups of users with different levels of experience. Finally, we used the measure 4 (“I’m satisfied by using this app”) as a dependent variable in a regression model.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Based on the traditional cut-off point of Eigenvalue greater than 1, results of exploratory factor analysis (table 1) shows the emergence of 3 factors that account for approximately 65% of variance in the sample analyzed. Factor 1 accounts for most variance in the data and suggests a set of emotional responses characterized by certain “Appreciation” (affection) of users toward the app analyzed. Factor 2 is composed

of measures related to the security users have that the app is going to work when they need and it is not going to fail. Taken together these measures suggest an emotional response related to “Security”. Results of factor 3 do not provide enough evidence of a consistent emotional response, like in the case of other two factors. For this reason, we decided not use the factor 3 and use the measure 6 (“I’m satisfied by using this app”) as our dependent variable in a regression model.

	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3
	Appreciation	Security	Not defined
I feel:			
Involved	0,67		
Freedom	0,73		
Excited			0,87
Satisfied			0,70
I can always have it		0,80	
I would miss it	0,69		
I trust it		0,78	
Proud	0,64		
Enjoy	0,79		
Relax	0,67		
Enthusiastic	0,77		
I should be cautious		-0,72	
Eigenvalue	5,02	1,94	1,04
Variance	0,41	0,16	0,08
Cronbach Alpha	0,86	0,72	0,57

Table 1. Factor analysis.

Information about respondent’s experience with the app was collected, because we wanted to analyze how different levels of experience in using the app might be related with differences in emotional responses. Respondents were classified in three groups: 1) low level – the user has no or few experience in using the app; 2) medium level – the user has some experience in using the app; 3) high level – the user has a lot of experience in using the app. Table 2 shows the frequency distribution of respondents according to each of these three groups.

Groups	Frequency	Relative Freq.
1	9	18,4%
2	14	28,6%
3	26	53,1%
Total	49	100,0%

Table 2. Frequency of distribution.

Now, we test for mean differences of “appreciation” emotional response existent among groups of respondents with different levels of experience. Table 3 shows the Anova results for emotional response “appreciation”.

Appreciation				
Group	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	
1	3,022	0,602	9	
2	3,235	0,714	14	
3	3,810	0,638	26	
Total	3,501	0,725	49	
Analysis of Variance				
Source	SS	df	MS	F
Between groups	5,538	2	2,768	6.46***
Within groups	19,715	46	0,428	
Total	25,253	48	0,526	

Note: *** sig<0.01, **sig<0.05, *sig<0.1

Table 3. Anova results for emotional response “appreciation”.

The F-test value (6.46, sig <0.01) indicates that the groups differ in their appreciation to the app. We applied a Scheffe post-hoc test to examine differences among groups in more detail. Results show that users with low and medium level of experience do not differ in their appreciation emotional response towards the app. However, users with high level of experience differ from users with medium level (mean difference = 0.58, sig < 0.05) and low level of experience (mean difference = 0.79, sig. 0.05). Taken together, these results suggest that users who have more experience have higher appreciation for the app.

We also test for mean differences of “Security” emotional response existent among groups of respondents with different levels of experience. Table 4 shows the Anova results for emotional response “Security”.

Security				
Group	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	
1	1,042	0,236	9	
2	1,211	0,509	15	
3	1,075	0,488	28	
Total	1,109	0,459	52	
Analysis of Variance				
Source	SS	df	MS	F
Between groups	0,228	2	0,114	0.53
Within groups	10,516	49	0,215	
Total	10,744	51	0,211	

Note: ***sig<0.01, **sig<0.05, *sig<0.1

Table 4. Anova results for emotional response “security”.

The F-test value (0.53, sig=0.59) indicates that the groups do not differ in term of “Security” emotional response means. Although the lack of statistical significant mean differences among the groups, one result calls attention: users with higher level of experience do not have the higher mean for “Security” emotional response.

Finally, we used the measure 6 (“I’m satisfied by using this app”) as a dependent variable in a regression model to assess whether the variables “experience”, “appreciation”, and “security” are related to satisfaction of users with the app. We follow an iterative approach to refine our model. First, we created dummy variables for the three groups of users with different levels of experience to be used in the regression model. Then, we ran a full model including all variables to get information about residuals and potential outliers that could influence results. Residuals diagnostics results suggest that the data partially conform to the ordinary-least square regression requirements. Cooks distance results revealed the existence of four respondents who were abnormally influencing regression results, and we decided to exclude them from the final analysis. As a final step, we ran a regression model using the robust sandwich estimator to obtain robust standar erros and our final estimates. We assessed multicollinearity but found no problems among variables. Table 5 shows the regression results.

	Coefficient	Stand. Coef.	Std. Error	t
Constant	2,416	.	0,484	5,000
Appreciation	0,248	0,274	0,138	1.8*
Security	0,480	0,370	0,147	3.26***
Dummy group 2	-0,030	-0,026	0,261	-0,120
Dummy group 3	0,022	0,021	0,266	0,080
Note: *** sig<0.01, **sig<0.05, *sig<0.1. Group 1 is the baseline				

Table 5. Regression results.

Results show that our model explains almost 30% of variance in satisfaction of users ($R^2 = 0.297$). As expected from results of correlation table, experience of users with the app is not statistically significant to predict their satisfaction, as shown by the t-values for the dummy variables. On the other hand, the emotional response factors "Appreciation" (t-value = 1.80, sig < 0.10) and "Security" (t-value = 3.26, sig < 0.01) are important predictors of user satisfaction. According to the standardized coefficients estimates, "Security" is more important than "Appreciation" in predicting user satisfaction.

Taken together, these results suggest that more experience users tend to have higher "Appreciation" emotional responses toward the app analyzed. Both emotional response factors "Appreciation" and "Security" are important predictors of user satisfaction. However, "Security" is more important than "Appreciation" to predict satisfaction. It suggests that being secure that the app is going to work contributes more for user satisfaction than having good feelings about it. Finally, users with different levels of experience do not differ in their emotional response "Security".

CONCLUSION

This paper aimed to identify the kinds of pleasures involved in the interaction of mobile application users and how users with different levels of experience may differ in their emotional response, influencing the design for experience.

We gathered data from 49 Instagram app users with different levels of experience and run some statistical

analysis to investigate emotional responses with the app. Our results showed that the twelve emotional responses investigated can be reduced to two major factors: appreciation and security. Appreciation encompasses feelings related to pleasure while security encompasses feelings of concern and caution.

Our results showed that users with more experience have higher appreciation means than users with less experience, but we could not find any differences for security emotional response. This result suggests that the experience of using the app and the appreciation emotional response may result from the users' ability during usage of the app. More experienced users may know how to use multiple functions and, then, can take better advantage of the app. On the other hand, less experienced users may not know how to use app's function and get frustrated with their experience, decreasing the likelihood of satisfaction. This result also suggests that there may be a learning effect, which evolves along time, since frequency of app usage may provide users with the knowledge they need to use multiple functions.

Finally, results also show that appreciation and security are both important predictors of user satisfaction. However, the effect of security is higher than that of appreciation. This result suggests that users want to be able to use the app whenever they want and know that they can count on it. The design of this app should provide stability, so the users can trust it will always work as promised.

One limitation of our study is the sample size analyzed that involved users of Instagram app only. Future studies could involve users of other apps. Also, our sample is limited in the number of users who participate in our survey. Other studies could increase the number of respondents so the estimates can be better estimated. Another limitation is our theoretical framework because it is limited to Jordan (2000) perspective of emotional response. Future study should include the perspective and framework proposed by other authors in order to broaden the scope of emotional responses analyzed.

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